

- Excess of which vitamins and deficiency of which substances are characteristic of the population of our region?

- Ways to protect the human body from excess nitrates found in vegetables.

- Protecting the human body from the effects of heavy metals, radiation, poisoning by reagents [3].

- What foods should be eaten to lose weight?

- What are the dangers of collecting herbs, mushrooms, berries near highways?

- What are wastewater?

- What are freons? What is the danger of their use for the environment?

Not only in lessons, but also in seminar classes, it is necessary to use collective and group work of students. Group work has several advantages compared to traditional methods. The atmosphere of cooperation and mutual assistance prevailing in the lesson influences the development of interest in knowledge. The results of joint work are usually higher than when each student works separately.

Research homework assignments, project activities:

As practice shows, research tasks stimulate students to independent search for knowledge, contribute to the formation of experience in creative, research activities.

Examples:

1. Yeasts convert sucrose into monosaccharides using invertase. Write the equation for the corresponding chemical reaction. How to experimentally prove the action of invertase? Check at which temperature (+5, +35, +65°C) the efficiency of invertase action is higher.

2. Sympathetic ink from food products. Using the following liquids (of your choice): milk, lemon juice, apple juice, concentrated sugar solution, onion juice, make an inscription on a sheet of writing paper using a cotton swab. When the inscription dries, heat this sheet with an iron for several minutes. What happens to the inscription? Explain the observations.

Project activities should be organized when students already have a significant arsenal of knowledge, skills, and abilities, allowing them to demonstrate high activity and a certain degree of independence in the process of studying new material. If each student is involved in active creative activity, feels confident and free, then a situation of success naturally arises. In this case, cognitive interest and personal motivation contribute to better assimilation of knowledge.

In the process of performing research tasks and project activities, students master various ways of integrating information, learn to develop their own opinion based on the understanding of various experiences, ideas, and concepts, build conclusions and logical chains of evidence, express their thoughts clearly, confidently, and correctly to others.

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O'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA SUN'IY INTELEKTNI JORIY QILISH ORQALI TA'LIM TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimiga sun'iy intellektning (AI) joriy etilishi haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan. U AI sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadigan asosiy yo'nalishlarni, jumladan, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv muhitini, ma'muriy samaradorlikni oshirish va tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirishni ta'kidlaydi. Maqolada, shuningdek, oliy ta'limda sun'iy intellektni qabul qilish bilan bog'liq muammolar va axloqiy mulohazalar muhokama qilinadi, ma'lumotlar maxfiyligi, algoritmik shaffoflik va Aidan mas'uliyatli foydalanish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Umuman olganda, u O'zbekistondagi oliy ta'lim kelajagini shakllantirishda sun'iy intellektning transformatsion salohiyati haqida qimmatli fikrlarni taqdim etadi. 1. Sun'iy intellektga asoslangan o'quv muhitlari

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt (AI), Oliy ta'lim, O'zbekiston, Ma'muriy samaradorlik, Tadqiqot va innovatsiyalar, Ma'lumotlarning maxfiyligi, Algoritmik shaffoflik, Mas'uliyatli AI, Transformativ ta'sir

AI O'zbekistonda oliy ta'limda inqilob qiladigan asosiy yo'nalishlardan biri bu shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim muhitini yaratishdir. AI algoritmlari ta'lim mazmunini moslashtirish uchun o'quvchilarning o'rganish naqshlari, afzalliklari va kuchli tomonlarini tahlil qiladi. Ushbu shaxsiylashtirilgan yondashuv nafaqat o'quvchilarning faolligini oshiradi, balki individual ehtiyojlarni yanada samarali hal qilish orqali ta'lim natijalarini yaxshilaydi.

Bundan tashqari, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan o'quv platformalari talabalar va o'qituvchilar uchun real vaqt rejimida fikr-mulohazalarni taqdim etishi mumkin. Moslashuvchan ta'lim tizimlari o'quvchilar qiyinchilik tug'diradigan sohalarni aniqlashi va qo'shimcha resurslar yoki shaxsiy repetitorlik kabi maqsadli tadbirlarni taklif qilishi va shu bilan umumiy ta'lim tajribasini oshirishi mumkin.

Ma'muriy samaradorlikni oshirish, AI oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ma'muriy jarayonlarni soddalashtirish uchun ham qo'llanilmoqda. Qabullarni boshqarish, kurslarni rejalashtirish va talabalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash xizmatlari kabi vazifalar sun'iy intellektga asoslangan avtomatlashtirishdan foydalanishi mumkin. Tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash (NLP) algoritmlari bilan ta'minlangan chatbotlar muntazam so'rovlarni ko'rib chiqish uchun tobora ko'proq qo'llanilayapti, bu esa ma'muriy xodimlarni yanada murakkab masalalar va strategik tashabbuslarga e'tibor qaratish uchun bo'shatish imkonini beradi.

Bundan tashqari, sun'iy intellektga asoslangan ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish vositalari universitetlarga katta hajmdagi talabalar va institutsional ma'lumotlarni to'plash va tahlil qilishda yordam beradi. Ushbu ma'lumotlarga asoslangan yondashuv qarorlarni yaxshiroq qabul qilish, talabalar muvaffaqiyati uchun bashoratli modellashirish va talabalarni saqlab qolish va bitiruv darajasini qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun ko'proq maqsadli tadbirlarni amalga oshirish imkonini beradi.

Tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarga yordam berish. O'qitish va ma'muriy funksiyalarni kuchaytirishdan tashqari, sun'iy intellekt O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim sektorida tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarni faollashtirmoqda. AI algoritmlari tadqiqot ma'lumotlarini tahlil qilish, naqshlarni aniqlash va turli fanlar bo'yicha ilmiy kashfiyotlar va yutuqlarni tezlashtirishi mumkin bo'lgan tushunchalarni yaratish uchun qo'llaniladi.

Bundan tashqari, mashinani o'rganish va tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash kabi sun'iy intellektga asoslangan texnologiyalar tadqiqotchilarga murakkab muammolarga innovatsion yechimlarni ishlab chiqish imkoniyatini beradi. Sog'liqni saqlashdan qishloq xo'jaligigacha, AI fanlararo hamkorlikni osonlashtiradi va butun jamiyatga foyda keltiradigan muhim sohalarda taraqqiyotga yordam beradi.

Muammolarni hal qilish va axloqiy AI ni ta'minlash. O'zbekiston oliy ta'limda sun'iy intellektni qo'llayotgani sababli, ma'lumotlar maxfiyligi, algoritmik tarafkashlik va axloqiy jihatlar kabi muammolarni ham hal qilishi kerak. Ma'lumotlarni himoya qilishning mustahkam choralari, AI algoritmlarida shaffoflik va Aidan mas'uliyatli foydalanish bo'yicha doimiy treninglar axloqiy AI tizimining muhim tarkibiy qismlaridir.

Bundan tashqari, AI qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga sarmoya kiritish va akademiya, sanoat va hukumat o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirish O'zbekistonning sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlarini yanada mustahkamlashi va oliy ta'lim sektorida barqaror o'sishni ta'minlashi mumkin.

Kelajakdagi istiqbol. O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellektning joriy etilishi texnologik jihatdan ilg'or va talabalarga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim muhiti sari muhim qadamdir. Sun'iy intellekt rivojlanishda davom

etar ekan, innovatsiyalar, tadqiqotlarning mukammalligi va global hamkorlik imkoniyatlari kengayib, O'zbekistonni sun'iy intellektga asoslangan ta'lim va bilimlarni yaratish markazi sifatida joylashtiradi.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, sun'iy intellektning (AI) O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimiga integratsiyalashuvi yanada ilg'or va talabalarga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim muhiti tomon muhim siljishni anglatadi. O'zbekistondagi universitet va kollejlarda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali o'qitish metodologiyasini yaxshilashi, ma'muriy jarayonlarni yaxshilashi, turli fanlar bo'yicha tadqiqot va innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirishi mumkin. Biroq, bu transformativ sayohat axloqiy AI tamoyillariga, jumladan ma'lumotlar maxfiyligi, algoritmik shaffoflik va mas'uliyatli foydalanishga asoslangan bo'lishi kerak. Strategik yondashuv va sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlariga doimiy sarmoya kiritish bilan O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim sektori ijobiy ta'lim natijalari va jamiyatga ta'sir ko'rsatish uchun texnologiyalardan foydalanishda yetakchilik qilishga tayyor.

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ANALITIK KIMYO TA'LIMIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING MUAMMOLARI XUSUSIDA

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